

Interactive Whiteboard Utilization and Students' Academic Performance in Basic Science in Public Secondary Schools in Ibiono Local Government, Akwa Ibom State

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Abstract

The study investigated the influence of interactive whiteboard utilisation on students' academic performance in basic science in public secondary schools in Ibiono Local Government, Akwa Ibom State. This study adopted a quasi-experimental research design to determine the influence of interactive whiteboard utilisation on students' academic performance in basic science in public secondary schools in Ibiono Local Government, Akwa Ibom State. The population of the study consisted of all 1503 public senior secondary school students in the Ibiono Ibom Local Government Area of Akwa Ibom State during the 2025/2026 academic year. The sample size of the study consisted of 120 basic science students drawn from two coeducational schools through a purposive sampling technique. The instrument Basic Science Performance Test (BSPT) was used for the collection of data. The instrument was validated by three experts, two from the Department of Science Education and one from the Psychological Foundation of Education. The reliability of the instrument was calculated using Kuder-Richardson 20, and the overall reliability coefficient stood at 0.88, which was deemed adequate for the study. Mean and standard deviation were used to answer the research questions, while analysis of covariance (ANCOVA) was used to test the null hypotheses. All the hypotheses were tested at .05 levels of significance. The study indicated

that there is a significant difference in academic performance of students taught using interactive whiteboard utilisation and those taught without it in basic science in public secondary schools in Ibiono Local Government, Akwa Ibom State. The study recommended that interactive whiteboards should be used more in the teaching and learning of basic science concepts to improve students' academic performance. The use of an interactive whiteboard in teaching and learning basic science will help the students to appreciate the concept being taught better and improve on their performance and interest.

Keyword: Interactive whiteboard utilisation, students' academic performance, gender and basic science.

Introduction

The poor academic performance of students in basic science has generated a lot of issues in nearly all educational institutions, particularly in Akwa Ibom State. The basic sciences are defined as the scientific disciplines of mathematics, physics, chemistry, and biology. They are called 'basic sciences' because they provide a fundamental understanding of natural phenomena and the processes by which natural resources are transformed (Aminu and Abubakar 2023). The study of basic science helps students to understand the living systems and life processes. This knowledge helps students to have better ways to predict, prevent, diagnose, and treat disease (Alao, 2018). Through basic science, students are trying to answer fundamental questions about how life works (Aminu and Abubakar, 2023). Basic science is one of the subjects offered in Nigerian schools, which is a prerequisite for further studies at higher institutions of learning, such as medicine, biochemistry, anatomy, physiology and agriculture, among others. Despite the importance of basic science, students' academic performance has been poor in the subject, and most basic science teachers have not undergone professional development to acquire competencies for effective lesson delivery. There is a need for teachers to improve the quality of teaching through professional development that will equip them with the contemporary method for teaching basic science, especially at secondary school levels, to enhance students' academic performance.

The contemporary methods for teaching and learning science which are capable of achieving the objectives of the school and society and increasing students' academic performance are those which emphasise effective use of innovative instructional aids and methods like projectors, interactive whiteboards, videotapes, film strips, cooperative

learning and the guided inquiry method, among others (Alao, 2018; Bati and Workneh, 2021). Academic performance is the outcome of education, as it indicates the extent to which the student, teacher, and curriculum in the educational institution have achieved the predetermined educational goals. Academic performance is the academic achievement of students in school subjects as measured by the results of examinations or tests given (Engel, 2022). Academic performance is generally used to determine how well an individual is able to assimilate, retain, recall and communicate his knowledge of what has been learnt.

Students' academic performance over the year has been dwindling, and the poor academic performance despite the importance of basic sciences. Aliyu (2023) reported that many factors, such as lack of teaching aids, teacher knowledge of subject matter, students' interest in learning, learning environment, teaching strategies and learning resources employed by the teacher. Mildrid (2021) also pointed out that the poor academic performance of students in basic science could be attributed to many factors, among which lack of teaching aids like interactive whiteboards is considered a major factor.

An interactive whiteboard is a teaching aid that helps in the teaching and learning of basic science. An electronic device. An interactive whiteboard is an electronic teaching aid designed for teachers to convey facts and ideas to the students in the classroom (Adams and Onwadi 2020). Interactive whiteboards help to develop proper images where students see, hear, taste, smell and understand properly. Teaching using an interactive whiteboard provides students with a complete example for conceptual thinking, creates an environment of interest for the students, increases the vocabulary of students and makes learning permanent. It also provides direct experience to the students (Bati and Workneh, 2021). According to Thompson (2023), the use of a whiteboard in the teaching and learning process creates a rich learning environment in terms of writing and explaining, increases the quality of education, and improves student academic performance and class participation.

Effective use of an interactive whiteboard in teaching and learning basic science enables students to learn better by having information presented through multiple modalities, especially through visual means (Mayer, 2023). Whiteboards are one of the teaching aids that enable the teachers to present facts to the students for effective learning (Bell, 2020). The use of interactive whiteboards, an innovative teaching tool, helps to engage students in the lesson content, learning process and academic performance. Odehe (2020) reported that the purpose of utilising an interactive whiteboard in the teaching and learning of basic science is to assist the teacher with presentation, transmission of educational content to the students for easy understanding and enhancement of academic

performance. According to Adeola (2020), students taught using an interactive whiteboard performed significantly better than those taught without an interactive whiteboard.

The use of an interactive whiteboard in teaching and learning basic science helps in enhancing students' academic performance, achievement of educational goals, acquisition of educational knowledge and understanding of basic science concepts (Tuma, 2021). Interactive whiteboard usage in teaching and learning basics helps to motivate students to learn, develop creativity, enhance prior knowledge and encourage the process of understanding (Dudar *et al.*, 2021). It also assists in decoding, organising and synthesising educational content; logical thinking; reasoning; communication; and interaction to improve students' academic performance. The use of an interactive whiteboard also contributes to students' development and acquisition of different skills as well as retention of desirable knowledge, skills and attributes. Comparing an interactive whiteboard with an ordinary blackboard, Marzano (2019) reported that the use of a whiteboard helps to enhance students' academic performance and arouse students' interest during the teaching of basic science.

Integrating an interactive whiteboard with more technologically enhanced classroom tools is one of the most recent trends in education. Interactive whiteboards which combine a whiteboard with a projector, desktop or laptop computer and a touch-sensitive surface are becoming common (Masley, 2025). As many as 15% of all classrooms are more equipped with some type of interactive whiteboard. This teaching tool is incorporated into the teaching and learning process to provide unlimited possibilities to enhance students' academic performance, teaching and learning. According to Kent (2017), interactive whiteboards promote intellectual quality within the classroom and ensure that lessons are relevant and significant to students, linking teaching, learning and assessment together.

The importance of a whiteboard cannot be overemphasised; it helps students to participate in the classroom and arouse and also simulate student interest to learn effectively in the classroom. According to Kent (2017), when the whiteboard is properly used in lessons, it helps to enhance student academic performance in schools. Whiteboards also provide ease of presentation (John, 2024). A teacher can easily deliver the subject by writing on the board because students cannot like oral presentations without some writing being done. Whiteboards enable the student to understand the topic being learnt. An interactive whiteboard, according to Benjamin (2020), enables the teacher to embrace the students' world and teaching within this context by drawing clear connections with prior knowledge, experiences and interests, and this can be achieved easier through the digital

tools that are available on an interactive whiteboard. Effective use of interactive whiteboards helps in enhancing students' academic performance irrespective of gender.

Gender, according to Saidu (2018), is a term used in describing behaviours and attributes expected of an individual on the basis of being born as either male or female. Gender differences in academic performance in basic science have been a long-debated issue. Various studies have shown male students performed better than their female counterparts. Oliver (2020) found male students performed better than female students in basic science irrespective of teaching methods used by the teacher. Nzewi (2019) and Adeola (2020) reported that male and female students performed equally in basic science subjects when taught using an interactive whiteboard and also given equal opportunities and facilities. Ashid (2019) found that teaching using an interactive whiteboard helps to enhance students' academic performance and retention irrespective of gender. Based on this background, the present study investigated the influence of interactive whiteboard utilisation on students' academic performance in basic science in public secondary schools in Ibiono Local Government, Akwa Ibom State.

Statement of Problem

The use of teaching aids plays a pivotal role in students' performance at any level of education. Over the years, there has been a public outcry by the students in basic science due to poor teaching of the concept and academic performance. The problem of poor performance of students in basic science has been blamed on poor teaching as a major factor. This has been attributed to many reasons, among which are the way and manner basic science teachers are handled and presented, evidenced in the inability of the teachers to provide for the specific learning needs of individual students. This leads to poor academic performance of students in basic science. The researcher observed that persistent use of an ordinary whiteboard and conveying instructions to a large class size in basic science without any recourse to effective use of an interactive whiteboard, despite the instructional value, is one of the major reasons affecting students' academic performance in the subject. The problem of this study, posed as a question, is could lack of utilisation of a whiteboard lead to students' poor academic performance in basic science? Based on this background, the present study therefore investigated the influence of interactive whiteboard utilisation on students' academic performance in basic science in public secondary schools in Ibiono Local Government, Akwa Ibom State.

Purpose of the Study

The primary purpose of the study was to investigate the influence of interactive whiteboard utilisation on students' academic performance in basic science in public secondary schools in Ibiono Local Government, Akwa Ibom State. The specific objectives are the following:

1. To determine the difference between the academic performance of basic science students when taught using an interactive whiteboard and those taught without an interactive whiteboard
2. To determine the difference between the academic performance of male and female basic science students when taught using an interactive whiteboard and those taught without an interactive whiteboard

Research questions

The following research questions were raised for the study:

1. What is the difference between the academic performance of basic science students taught using an interactive whiteboard and those taught without an interactive whiteboard in public secondary schools in Ibiono Local Government, Akwa Ibom State?
2. What is the difference between the academic performance of male and female basic science students taught using an interactive whiteboard and those taught without an interactive whiteboard in public secondary schools in Ibiono Local Government, Akwa Ibom State?

Research Hypotheses

The following hypotheses were formulated at the 0.05 level of significance for the study:

1. There is no significant difference between the academic performance of basic science students taught using an interactive whiteboard and those taught without an interactive whiteboard in public secondary schools in Ibiono Local Government, Akwa Ibom State.
2. There is no significant difference between the academic performance of male and female basic science students taught using an interactive whiteboard and those taught without an interactive whiteboard in public secondary schools in Ibiono Local Government, Akwa Ibom State.

Research Method

Design of the Study

This study adopted a pre-test post-test control group quasi-experimental research design to determine the influence of interactive whiteboard utilisation on students' academic performance in basic science in public secondary schools in Ibiono Local Government, Akwa Ibom State.

Population of the study

The target population of the study consisted of all 1503 public senior secondary school students in the Ibiono Ibom Local Government Area of Akwa Ibom State during the 2025/2026 academic year. The choice of this level of students was considered appropriate for the study because it is expected that these students have spent about five years in the school and are mature enough to think and make judgements and they would be able to answer questions related to the study.

Sample and Sampling Techniques

The sample size of the study consisted of 120 students drawn from two coeducational schools through a purposive sampling technique. The two educational after selecting the two co-educational secondary schools, the population of JSS2 basic science students was identified in their intact classes. A purposive sampling technique was used to select the sample size of 60 students from each of the two co-educational public secondary schools, making a total of 120 students for the study. The instrument Basic Science Performance Test (BSPT) was used for the collection of data in this study. This instrument contained twenty questions with the options A – D on whiteboard utilisation.

Validation of the instrument

The content of the instrument, the Basic Science Performance Test (BSPT), was validated by three experts, two from the department of science education and one from the psychological foundation of education, both in the Faculty of Education, University of Uyo, to scrutinise and assess the items and make corrections. These experts assessed the suitability of the instrument to ascertain whether or not the test items were congruent to the objective of the study.

Reliability of the Instrument

The reliability of the instruments, the Basic Science Performance Test (BSPT), was established using the trial testing method. The instruments were administered to 30 students who were not part of the actual study. The scores obtained from the tests were used to determine the reliability coefficients of the study using Kuder-Richardson 20, and the overall reliability coefficient stood at 0.88, which was deemed adequate for the study.

Experimental Procedure

The researcher collected an introductory letter from the departments in order to inform the principals of the schools selected for the study. An approval to conduct the research was duly given by the principal of the schools. For the purpose of data collection, the following procedures were followed:

Training of the research assistants

A one-week training programme was organised for the basic science teachers in the sampled schools to assist in the study. These basic science teachers were trained on how to teach using an interactive whiteboard. For the experimental and control groups, the researcher chose to supervise the regular class teachers of the experimental and control groups on how to use the mock teaching exercise and lesson plan prepared by the researcher. The researcher kept monitoring the research assistants (teachers) to ensure that they did not deviate from the procedure of instruction given to them. The basic science teachers in both the experimental and control groups were allowed to teach for 30 minutes to test their competence in teaching using an interactive whiteboard before carrying out the treatment on the subjects (experimental and control groups). The experiment lasted for two weeks. After the treatment, a posttest was administered to both the experimental and control groups in the two schools at the end of the two weeks, groups each with the same items as in the pretest. This was helpful to determine the mean score of the groups. After this test, results were collected for analysis.

Method of Data Analysis

Mean and standard deviation were used to answer the research questions, while analysis of covariance (ANCOVA) was used to test the null hypotheses. All the hypotheses were tested at .05 levels of significance.

Decision Rule: In testing the null hypotheses, if the calculated P-values at 0.05 significant levels are greater than the critical t-values, the null hypotheses are rejected; otherwise, they are retained.

Results

Research Question 1: What is the difference between academic performance of basic science students taught using interactive whiteboard and those taught without interactive white board in public secondary schools in Ibiono Local Government, Akwa Ibom State?

Table 1: Mean and Standard Deviation of difference between academic performance of basic science students taught using interactive white board and those taught without interactive white board in public secondary schools in Ibiono Local Government, Akwa Ibom State

Instructional Materials	N	Pretest		Posttest		Gain scores
		Mean	SD	Mean	SD	
Interactive white board	40	8.37	2.22	17.51	4.37	9.14
Without interactive white board	60	8.27	2.18	15.68	2.74	7.41

The result presented in Table 1 shows that the pretest mean scores of students taught using an interactive whiteboard and without an interactive whiteboard were 8.37 and 8.27 with the standard deviation of 2.22 and 2.18, respectively, indicating that all students were at the same cognitive level before treatment. On the other hand, the posttest mean scores of students taught flowering plants using an interactive whiteboard and without an interactive whiteboard were 17.51 and 17.69 with the standard deviations of 4.37 and 2.74, respectively, with the gain scores of 9.14 for the interactive whiteboard and 7.41 for without the interactive whiteboard, indicating that a difference exists between the academic performance of basic science students taught using an interactive whiteboard and those taught without an interactive whiteboard. This implies that an interactive whiteboard is effective in enhancing students' academic performance.

Research Question 2: What is the difference between the academic performance of male and female basic science students taught using an interactive whiteboard and those taught

without an interactive whiteboard in public secondary schools in Ibiono Local Government, Akwa Ibom State?

Table 2: Mean and Standard Deviation of academic performance of male and female basic science students taught using interactive white board and those taught without interactive white board in public secondary schools in Ibiono Local Government, Akwa Ibom State

Gender		Pretest			Posttest		Gain scores
		N	Mean	SD	Mean	SD	
Interactive whiteboard	Male	18	7.70	1.78	12.50	3.22	4.80
	Female	23	6.60	2.72	12.90	3.85	6.30
Without Interact whiteboard	Male	25	6.70	1.20	9.50	4.10	2.80
	Female	35	6.66	1.22	8.90	4.55	2.24

The result presented in Table 2 shows that the pre-test performance mean scores of male and female students taught using an interactive whiteboard were 7.70 and 6.60, respectively, with the standard deviation of 1.78 for males and 2.72 for females. Also, the pre-test performance mean scores of male and female students taught without an interactive whiteboard were 6.70 and 6.66, respectively, with the standard deviation of 1.20 for males and 2.22 for females, indicating that male students performed better than the female students before treatment. However, the posttest performance mean scores for male and female students taught using an interactive whiteboard were 12.50 and 12.90, with the standard deviations of 3.22 and 3.85, respectively, and performance gain scores of 4.80 for male and 6.30 for female students. The posttest performance mean scores for male and female students taught without an interactive whiteboard were 9.50 and 8.90, with the standard deviations of 4.10 and 4.55, respectively, and performance gain scores of 2.80 for male and 2.20 for female students. The result indicated that differences exist between the academic performance of male and female basic science students taught using an interactive whiteboard and those taught without an interactive whiteboard. This indicates that interactive whiteboards have relative effects on both male and female students' academic performance in basic science.

Research Hypothesis 1: There is no significant difference between the academic performance of basic science students when taught using an interactive whiteboard and those taught without an interactive whiteboard in public secondary schools in Ibiono Local Government, Akwa Ibom State.

Table 3: Summary of Analysis of Covariance (ANCOVA) of the difference between academic performance of basic science students when taught using interactive white board and those taught without interactive white board in public secondary schools in Ibiono Local Government, Akwa Ibom State

Source	Type III Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	Decision at p<.05 alpha
Corrected model	4162.217	1	4162.217	59.00	.000	S
Intercept	42.022	1	42.022	.60	.000	S
Pretest	8.235	1	8.235	.12	.000	S
Treatment *	472.099	1	472.009	9.10	.000	S
Error	5290.650	102	51.86	-	-	-
Total	266849.00	116	-	-	-	-
Corrected Total	9997.88	120	-	-	-	-

a. R Squared = .470 (Adjusted R Squared = .456)

The result presented in Table 3 above revealed that the F-value of 9.10 obtained at 1 and 116 degrees of freedom had an associated p-value of 0.000, which is less than the 0.05 alpha level. Therefore, the null hypothesis is rejected; hence, there is a significant difference between the academic performance of basic science students when taught using an interactive whiteboard and those taught without an interactive whiteboard in public secondary schools in Ibiono Local Government, Akwa Ibom State.

Research Hypothesis 2 There is no significant difference between the academic performance of male and female basic science students when taught using an interactive whiteboard and those taught without an interactive whiteboard in public secondary schools in Ibiono Local Government, Akwa Ibom State

Table 4: Summary of Analysis of Covariance (ANCOVA) of difference between difference between academic performance of male and female basic science students when taught using interactive white board and those taught without interactive white board in public secondary schools in Ibiono Local Government, Akwa Ibom State

Source	Type III Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	Decision at p<.05 alpha
Pretest(Covariate)	4162.210	1	4162.210	96.51	.000	S
Treatment	43.125	1	43.125	.60	.443	s
Gender	6.211	1	8.211	.12	.734	s
Treatment *	423.000	1	483.000	9.32	.780	s
Error	5280.600	102	51.77	-	-	-
Total	266849.000	116	-	-	-	-
Corrected Total	9997.880	120	-	-	-	-

a. R Squared = .470 (Adjusted R Squared = .456)

The result is presented in Table 4. Above revealed that the F-value of 9.32 obtained at 1 and 116 degrees of freedom had an associated p-value of 0.780, which is greater than the 0.05 alpha level. Hence, the null hypothesis is accepted; there is a significant difference between the academic performance of male and female basic science students when taught using an interactive whiteboard and those taught without an interactive whiteboard in public secondary schools in Ibiono Local Government, Akwa Ibom State.

Discussion of Findings

The result presented in Table 1 indicated that a difference exists between the academic performance of basic science students taught using an interactive whiteboard and those taught without an interactive whiteboard. The study also indicated that an interactive whiteboard is effective in enhancing students' academic performance. The corresponding hypothesis in Table 3 showed that there is a significant difference between the academic performance of basic science students when taught using an interactive whiteboard and those taught without an interactive whiteboard in public secondary schools in Ibiono Local Government, Akwa Ibom State. This result may be due to the fact that an interactive

whiteboard is effective in enhancing students' academic performance in basic science. This finding is in line with the finding of Odehe (2020), who reported that the purpose of utilising an interactive whiteboard in the teaching and learning of basic science is to assist the teacher with presentation, transmission of educational content to the students for easy understanding and enhancement of academic performance. According to Adeola (2020), students taught using an interactive whiteboard performed significantly better than those taught without an interactive whiteboard. According to Kent (2017), when the whiteboard is properly used in lessons, it helps to enhance student academic performance in schools. Interactive whiteboards also provide ease of presentation. A teacher can easily deliver the subject by writing on the board because students cannot like oral presentations without some writing being done.

The result presented in Table 2 indicated that a difference exists between the academic performance of male and female basic science students taught using an interactive whiteboard and those taught without an interactive whiteboard. The result also indicated that interactive whiteboards have relative effects on both male and female students' academic performance in basic science. The corresponding hypothesis in Table 4 shows that there is a significant difference between the academic performances of male and female basic science students when taught using an interactive whiteboard and those taught without an interactive whiteboard in public secondary schools in Ibiono Local Government, Akwa Ibom State. The finding is in line with the finding of Nzewi (2019) and Adeola (2020), who reported that male and female students performed equally in basic science subjects when taught using an interactive whiteboard and also given equal opportunities and facilities. Ashid (2019) found that teaching using an interactive whiteboard helps to enhance students' academic performance and retention irrespective of gender. Teaching using an interactive whiteboard provides students with a complete example for conceptual thinking, creates an environment of interest for the students, increases the vocabulary of students and makes learning permanent. It also provides direct experience to the students. According to Thompson (2023), the use of a whiteboard in the teaching and learning process creates a rich learning environment in terms of writing and explaining, increases the quality of education, and improves student academic performance and class participation.

Conclusion

Based on the finding of the study, it is concluded that interactive whiteboard utilisation has significant influence on students' academic performance in basic science in public

secondary schools in Ibiono Local Government, Akwa Ibom State. This is so because it was concluded that students taught using interactive white board performed significantly better than those taught without interactive white board irrespective of gender. This implies that differences exist between the academic performance of male and female basic science students taught using an interactive whiteboard and those taught without an interactive whiteboard.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of the study, the following recommendations are made:

1. An interactive whiteboard should be used more in the teaching and learning of basic science to improve students' academic performance. This is because the use of an interactive whiteboard in teaching and learning basic science will help the students to appreciate the concept being taught better and improve on their performance and interest.
2. School administrators should organise seminars for both teachers and students on effective use of interactive whiteboards during teaching and learning processes.
3. The curriculum planners should plan the nation's curriculum to accommodate the use of interactive whiteboards for teaching students and should allot more time to basic science teachers in the school timetable to allow for proper implementation of basic science concepts.

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